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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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cerebellar disorders and, less frequently, extrapyramidal disorders are mentioned. In the structure of chronic encephalopathy in hypothyroidism, psychoemotional and intellectual disorders are most often described [7,9].

The polymorphism of the clinical picture of mental lesions in patients with hypothyroidism has been described by domestic and foreign authors, including fundamental works by V.G. Baranov (1966) and I.D. Levit (1977), as well as by A.K. Dobrzanskaya (1973), B.V. Drivotinov and M.Z. Klebanov (1989), A.P. Kalinin and S.V. Kotov (2009).

However, there is still no consensus on the features of quality of life (QL) in patients with hypothyroidism. Assessment of health-related quality of life has become an obligatory attribute of modern research. It allows to determine the impact of the disease or a particular disorder on the state of the patient's key functions, the real effectiveness of therapy and rehabilitation programmes, as well as to predict the course and outcome of the disease. All of the above shows the relevance of the problem and the expediency of its study in the clinic.

Purpose of the study. To determine the quality of life in patients with primary hypothyroidism depending on sex using standardised indicators of SF-36 questionnaire scales.

Study material. 111 patients with primary hypothyroidism aged from 18 to 59 years, mean age 38,2±7,6 years were examined.

Patients of the endocrinology and neurology department of Andijan State Medical Institute were taken under observation. The patients were observed at the endocrinology and neurology department of AndMI. The cause of primary hypothyroidism (PHT) in all patients was autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT). All patients signed informed consent to participate in the study.

Thus, the inclusion criteria for the study were: age between 18 and 59 years, presence of subclinical hypothyroidism (SH) and manifest hypothyroidism (MH). Patients with psychiatric and severe somatic diseases and thyroid gland (thyroid) diseases accompanied by thyrotoxicosis syndrome in anamnesis; menopausal syndrome requiring estrogen replacement hormone therapy; diabetes mellitus; autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome; pregnant and lactating women were excluded from the study.

Table 1.

Distribution of patients by groups and subgroups

Groups	Forms of HT	subgroups	floor	n	%
I group (n=73), 65,8 %	women	A-subgroup	MST	41	56,20%
		B-subgroup	SGT	32	43,80%
Group II (n=38), 34,2%	men	A-subgroup	MGT	23	60,50%
		B-subgroup	MST	15	39,50%
Total IHT patients				64	57,70%
Total patients with SST				47	42,30%
Total				111	100,00%

Patients were divided into 2 groups according to their sex. Group I included 73 (65.8 %) female patients, group II - 38 (34.2 %) male patients. Each group was divided into 2 subgroups depending on the form of primary hypothyroidism. Subgroup "A" - 64 patients with manifest form of HT, subgroup "B" - 47 patients with subclinical form of HT. Subgroup "A" of group I included 41 (56.2 %) patients, subgroup "A" of group II - 23 (60.5 %). Subgroup "B" of group I included 32 (43.8 %) patients, subgroup "B" of group II - 15 (39.5 %). The control group consisted of 20 healthy individuals, comparable with the main groups by sex and age.

The examined patients with primary hypothyroidism were aged from 48 to 59 years. The mean age of women was 42.1±11.7 years and the mean age of men was 48.2±8.3 years ($p>0.05$).

All patients underwent standard clinical and neurological examination (analysis of patients' complaints, life history and medical history, objective examination, including the study of neurological status) and somatic examination.

The Brief Mental Status Evaluation Scale (MMSE) was used to objectify cognitive impairment. The maximum score was 30 points, which corresponds to the optimal state of cognitive functions. The lower the final score, the more pronounced the cognitive deficit. In terms of the number of tasks, the MMSE significantly exceeds other tests and requires more time to conduct, experts note the rather low sensitivity of the test. Also for neuropsychological testing we used a method using a short scale - the frontal lobe dysfunction test battery [BLD]. Frontal Assessment Battery (FAB). In the diagnosis of dementia with predominantly frontal lobe involvement, comparison of FAB results is of value. Frontal dementia is indicated by an extremely low FAB score (less than 11 points). The connection of cognitive disorders with vascular factors was established using the Hachinski scale (SH) - in the presence of 7 points and higher (average 12-14 points) [2,3]. Quality of life (QoL) of patients with PHT was investigated using the SF-36 General Health Questionnaire. The questionnaire was filled out by the patient independently or by interviewing the patient with written recording of his/her answers in the questionnaire form. The patients' QoL was assessed in points (1).

Statistical processing and visualisation of the results were performed using the statistical analysis software package STATISTICA v. 10 and built-in functions of Microsoft Office. 10 and built-in functions of Microsoft Office Excel. The critical significance level of the null statistical hypothesis was assumed to be 0.05.

Results of the study. It should be noted that the detection rate of comorbid pathology was higher in each group during MHT. Cerebrovascular pathology and metabolic syndrome in women with MHT were detected in 30.6% and 36.1% of cases, respectively.

Psychological history was assessed in the subjects of this project. The performance of the subjects was compared with that of the CG. Cognitive function (CF) scores on MMSE and FAB were significantly lower in MHT patients - 28.0 (27.0÷29.0) points and 17.0 (16.0÷18.0) points than in CG - 29.5 (28.0÷30.0) points ($p=0.006$) and 18.0 (17.0÷18.0) points ($p=0.022$). In patients with hypothyroidism KN according to MMSE and FAB were established in 70,5%.

Neuropsychological testing with assessment of memory, attention and thinking functions revealed in group I patients with high MMSE and FAB scores signs of CNs, which were one of the leading (72.5%) in the structure of HC lesions in hypothyroidism. In patients with hypothyroidism the proportion of mild KNs (LKN) was 46.8%, moderate KNs (MCN) - 30.6%, in 22.5% of cases KNs were not detected. (Table 2).

In group II patients, the proportion of mild CNs (LCNs) was 39.5%, which is significantly lower compared to the same indicators of group I ($p<0.005$). The percentage of moderate SCIs was 18.4%, with no SCIs detected in 42.1% of cases (t.4.6). compared to group I, and in group I patients with SCIs predominated over group II patients with SCIs - 42.1% vs. 12.3% (% calculation was based on the total number of patients within each group).

Regarding the identification of the degree of IP in patients in the subgroups, it can be said that patients with SGT in both groups had a higher percentage of patients without IP (Fig.1). In MGT of both groups, patients with UCN and LCN were significantly more frequent (48.8%, 43.9% and 30.4% and 39.1%, respectively). Figure 1 shows that a higher percentage of patients without SCN was found in both groups in IHT.

In patients with MST, 40.4% had short-term memory impairment, 44.2% had impaired memory performance, 84.6% had decreased memory rate, and 25.9% had impaired long-term memory. In terms of short-term memory, patients with MST without KN, with LCN and UCN differed significantly between themselves ($p<0.001$) and the comparison group ($p=0.001$). Memory productivity decreased predominantly in UCN ($p<0.05$), delayed recall - in patients with LCH and UCN ($p<0.05$). The increasing severity of ICH on the background of hypothyroidism decompensation was 45.2%; 45.2%; 9.6% without ICH LCH UCN was associated with impairments of long-term memory and memory productivity, because in patients with UCN with increasing levels of TTG the number of words reproduced by the fifth presentation ($r_s=-0.69$; $p=0.020$) and in delayed reproduction ($r_s=-0.90$; $p<0.001$) decreased.

Attention dysfunction was found in 71.2% of patients with MGT. Decreased concentration of attention was found in 29.8%, increased instability and exhaustion of attention - in 47.1%. In 1.9% of cases there were signs of attention rigidity, in 22.1% - extremely fast pace of work. Decreased accuracy and concentration of attention prevailed in LCN ($p<0.001$); decreased stability of attention at the first ($p=0.003$) and second ($p=0.002$) minutes, increased time of sample performance ($p<0.001$) - in UCN.

Disorders of thinking function in MST were found in 52.9% and were characterised by slowed thinking activity (29.1%) with elements of concrete-situational thinking (40.0%), accelerated (3.6%) or rigid (23.7%) types of thinking in LCN and UCN, disorders of analytical-synthetic function (3.6%) - in UCN.

Clinical signs of anxiety (43.2%) and depression (20.2%) and their subclinical manifestations (24.0 and 26.9%) were found in patients with IHT. In hypothyroidism decompensation, patients with IHT had a higher level of anxiety than patients without IHT ($p=0.040$), and the level of depression was significantly different from patients with LCN ($p=0.020$), without IHT ($p=0.030$) and the comparison group ($p=0.020$).

Patients with IHT had a lower score on the Hachinski scale (SH) - 3.0 (2.0÷5.0) points than in the comparison group - 4.5 (3.0÷6.0) points ($p=0.006$). SHH score of 4 points and less was registered in hypothyroidism in 74.0%, 7 points and more - in 2.9%. The sum of scores from 5.0 to 6.0 on SHH was revealed in 23.1%, which indicated the contribution of cerebrovascular pathology in the development of CH in hypothyroidism.

We evaluated the contribution of detected CP disorders to the clinical manifestations of CN in hypothyroidism. The group to be analysed included KF disorders, for which a statistically significant association with the identified CNs was established: disorders of thinking ($\chi^2=26.87$; $p<0.001$), disorders of short-term ($\chi^2=56.83$; $p<0.001$) and long-term ($\chi^2=30.85$; $p<0.001$) memory, changes in productivity ($\chi^2=17.83$; $p<0.001$) and rate of remembering ($\chi^2=20.36$; $p<0.001$), disorders of attention concentration ($\chi^2=38.18$; $p<0.001$). Since there was no correlation between the identified EF, changes in psychoemotional status ($p=0.508$; $p=0.213$) and attention stability ($p=0.288$), these parameters were not included in the construction of the logistic regression model. According to the results of the analysis, we identified the CF disorders that contributed most to the clinical manifestations of CH in patients with hypothyroidism: short-term memory ($p<0.001$), attention concentration ($p=0.001$) and long-term memory ($p=0.028$).

Changes in the cognitive status of patients with MHT had a wave-like character of improvement - deterioration - improvement with increasing positive dynamics, which further consolidated and became stable. Taking into account that the process of information transfer from short-term to long-term memory is accompanied by functional and structural changes supported by the acetylcholinergic system, it can be assumed that neuroprotective therapy with Cortexin has a direct neurotrophic, neurometabolic effect on cells and mediators of the central nervous system, as well as an effect on visual memory, which can be associated with the improvement of connections between the frontoparietal lobes cortex and subcortical structures [6].

30 patients (15 men and 15 women) with MST were given a course of neuroprotective therapy using Cortexin 10 mg intramuscularly daily for 20 days. The main indices of MMSE and FAB scales were studied

in dynamics - before treatment and after the treatment. Also, 30 patients (15 men and 15 women) who did not receive neuroprotective therapy were studied to compare the dynamics of CN

In the group of patients who received Cortexin, we can see that there was a positive dynamics of MMSE and FAB scores, and in the group of female patients there was a greater increase in FAB scores compared to male patients. Recovery of long-term memory is more intensive in women (Fig. 4.10). In the group of patients who did not receive Cortexin no dynamics in the regression of FAB were observed.

We also studied the quality of life in the patients of the main study groups using standardised indicators of the SF-36 General Health Questionnaire scales.

The majority of the SF-36 questionnaire scales in Group I showed lower values of QoL indicators compared to those in Group II, the differences in QoL indicators were statistically significant, except for the indicators of the "physical functioning" and "general health" scales. Patients in the age groups did not have statistically significant differences in standardised measures of QoL on all scales of the SF-36 questionnaire.

The standardised measures of QoL on 8 scales of the SF-36 questionnaire (Me and ICR) in the patients of the main study groups (with LCR and UCD syndrome) in the groups. A statistically significant difference was revealed between the indicators of EF in group II: the indicators on the scale "physical functioning" and on the scale "vitality" were lower in patients with LCR syndrome ($U=22.5$, $p=0.032$ and $U=16$, $p=0.009$). For the other scales of the SF-36 questionnaire in Group II and for all scales in Group I, the QoL indicators had no statistically significant differences between the main studied groups of patients.

According to the data of our study, the QoL of patients with PHT was influenced by the profile of RBM. In patients with the RBM syndrome, attention deficit disorder showed a decrease in the PL indicator on the "psychological health" scale ($W=698.5$, $p=0.024$), dynamic praxis deficit disorder - on the "physical functioning" scale ($W=325$, $p=0.003$), and executive function deficit - on the "general health" scale ($W=673.5$, $p=0.024$). Disturbances in other cognitive spheres had no significant influence on the indicators of the EF according to the scales of the SF-36 questionnaire. Standardised indices of SF-36 questionnaire scales at detection of disturbances of attention, "executive" function and dynamic praxis in patients with PGT. In group II patients these indices of cognitive functions had not reliable differences with the CG indices, and in group I patients the scale differences on some scales of SF-36 questionnaire had a reliable profile in comparison with the CG.

Emotional-affective disorders influenced on the indices of the SF-36 questionnaire scales in patients with PHT. In patients with asthenic disorder, all the scales of the SF-36 questionnaire had lower QoL scores. In depressed patients, all scales of the SF-36 questionnaire except the "pain" scale ($K=4.7$, $p=0.095$) reduced the EF indices. In patients with heightened situational anxiety, all scales of the SF-36 questionnaire were reduced except for the "role physical functioning" scale ($K=5.52$, $p=0.063$). Increased personality anxiety influenced the QoL indicators only for those scales that assess the mental component of health, for the scales "physical functioning", "role physical functioning", "pain" and "general health" the QoL indicators did not change statistically significantly ($K=2.16$, $p=0.339$; $K=3.19$, $p=0.203$; $K=2.81$, $p=0.246$; $K=2.41$, $p=0.299$, respectively).

Conclusions. The CV of patients with PHT is influenced by the profile of cognitive impairment. A significant impact on the QoL of patients with PHT and UCD syndrome was made by impairments of "executive" function, including dynamic praxis. Patients with OCD syndrome who had impaired executive function according to the results of neuropsychological testing had lower QoL indicators on the "general health" scale, which characterises the physical state of health, resistance to illness and prospects for treatment, assessed by the patient himself. Praxis - the ability to acquire and use a variety of motor skills, memorised and automated sequences of movements. Decrease in the "physical functioning" scale in case of praxis impairment confirms the direct relation of regulatory SCs to self-care and daily physical activity of patients. In patients with PHT and UCD syndrome, impaired attention

was correlated with a lower score on the SF-36 "psychological health" scale of the questionnaire. This meant that patients with RBM syndrome

and attention deficit disorder had anxiety and depressive states, which determine the psychological well-being of these patients.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ КАРТИНЫ ВИРУСНЫХ ЭНЦЕФАЛИТОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Энцефалит— это воспаление паренхимы головного мозга, возникающее в результате прямой вирусной инвазии или как постинфекционное иммунологическое осложнение, вызванное реакцией гиперчувствительности на вирус или другой чужеродный белок. Пациенты с энцефалитом в большинстве случаев нуждаются в длительном лечении в условиях специализированного стационара, требуют проведения многочисленных дорогостоящих диагностических исследований и зачастую имеют неблагоприятные клинические исходы, включая потерю трудоспособности и смерть, что может быть обусловлено неадекватными подходами к диагностике и тактике ведения данной категории больных.

Ключевые слова: вирусный энцефалит, головной мозг, паренхима головного мозга

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KATTALARDA VIRUSLI ENSEFALIT KLINIK TASVIRINING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ensefalit-bu to'g'ridan-to'g'ri virusli invaziya natijasida yoki virusga yoki boshqa begona oqsilga yuqori sezuvchanlik reaksiyasi natijasida kelib chiqadigan infeksiyadan keyingi immunologik asorat sifatida yuzaga keladigan miya parenximasining yallig'lanishi. Ensefalit bilan og'rigan bemorlar ko'p hollarda ixtisoslashgan shifoxonada uzoq muddatli davolanishga muhtoj, ko'plab qimmat diagnostika tadqiqotlarini talab qiladi va ko'pincha salbiy klinik natijalarga, shu jumladan nogironlik va o'limga olib keladi, bu esa ushbu toifadagi bemorlarni tashxislash va boshqarish taktikasiga etarli bo'lmagan yondashuvlar bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: virusli ensefalit, miya, miya parenximasi

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PECULIARITIES OF THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF VIRAL ENCEPHALITIS IN ADULTS

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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